

LIBRI

www.libridergi.org

Epigrafi, Çeviri ve Eleştiri Dergisi

Journal of Epigraphy, Reviews and Translations

Sayı **VII** (2021)

Two New Epitaphs from Termessos

Nihal TÜNER ÖNEN & Murat ARSLAN

Libri: Epigrafi, Çeviri ve Eleştiri Dergisi'nde bulunan içeriklerin tümü kullanıcılara açık, serbestçe/ücretsiz "açık erişimli" bir dergidir. Kullanıcılar, yayıncıdan ve yazar(lar)dan izin almaksızın, dergideki kitap tanıtımlarını, eleştirileri ve çevirileri tam metin olarak okuyabilir, indirebilir, dağıtabilir, çıktısını alabilir ve kaynak göstererek bağlantı verebilir.

Libri, uluslararası hakemli elektronik (online) bir dergi olup değerlendirme süreci biten kitap tanıtımları, eleştiriler ve çeviriler derginin web sitesinde (libridergi.org) yıl boyunca ilgili sayının içinde (Sayı VII: Ocak-Aralık 2021) yayımlanır. Aralık ayı sonunda ilgili yıla ait sayı tamamlanır.

Dergide yayımlanan eserlerin sorumluluğu yazarlarına aittir.

Atıf Düzeni Tüner-Önen N. & Arslan M. 2021, "Two New Epitaphs from Termessos". *Libri* VII, 227-234.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5808719

Geliş Tarihi: 07.09.2021 | Kabul Tarihi: 10.11.2021

Elektronik Yayın Tarihi: 28.12.2021

Editörya: Phaselis Research Project
www.libridergi.org

Two New Epitaphs from Termessos

Termessos'tan İki Yeni Mezar Yazıtı

Nihal TÜNER ÖNEN * Murat ARSLAN **

Abstract: In the article discussed here, two new epitaphs discovered in the necropolis area called E3 during the surveys conducted in Termessos are introduced in 2019. Both epitaphs are dated to the Roman Imperial Period, but according to the gens names used in the inscriptions, the first epitaph is dated from before the Constitutio Antoniniana (212 A.D.), while the second is dated after it. The first inscription includes an epitaph by a priest named Thoas for his son Hermaios. As it is known from the inscription, Thoas is the priest of the Supreme God Dionysus. From inscriptions found earlier three priests of Dionysus are known from the city, but an inscription in which Dionysus is mentioned as the “Supreme God” is here documented for the first time. The worship of the god is mostly associated with the goddess Rome and the Emperor Cult in the city. In this article, three proposals are presented regarding the transcription of the letters ΠΡΟΙΜΩΝ related to the priest in this epitaph. The second epitaph concerns the tomb that Claudia Anna had built for herself and her family members. While the first epitaph does not include any statements of prohibition, punishment for burial and damnation, the other includes a statement of prohibition regarding “not burying someone else” and a penalty amount of 1500 denarii to be paid to Zeus Solymeus, the chief god of the city.

Keywords: Termessos, Epitaph, Dionysus, Zeus Solymeus, Pisidia

Öz: Burada ele alınan makalede Termessos kentinde gerçekleştirilen 2019 yılı yüzey araştırmaları sırasında E3 olarak adlandırılan *necropolis* alanında tespit edilmiş iki yeni mezar yazıtı tanıtılmaktadır. Her iki yazıt da Roma İmparatorluk Dönemi'ne tarihlenir, fakat yazıtlarda kullanılan *gens* isimlerine göre ilk yazıt *Constitutio Antoniniana*'dan (MS 212) önceye tarihlenirken, ikinci yazıt sonrasına tarihlenir. İlk yazıt Thoas adındaki bir rahibin oğlu Hermaios için yaptırdığı mezar yazıtını içerir. Yazıttan öğrenildiği üzere Thoas Yüce Tanrı Dionysos'un rahibidir. Daha önce ele geçen yazıtlar aracılığıyla kantten üç Dionysos rahibi tanınmaktadır, fakat Dionysos'un “Yüce Tanrı” olarak ünlendiği bir yazıt ilk kez belgelenmektedir. Tanrının tapımı kentte daha çok tanrıça Roma ve İmparator Kültü'yle birlikte anılmaktadır. Makalede, söz konusu yazıtta geçen ve rahip ile ilişkilendirilen ΠΡΟΙΜΩΝ harflerinin deşifreyonuna ilişkin üç öneri sunulmaktadır. İkinci yazıt, Claudia Anna'nın kendisi ve aile fertleri için yaptırdığı mezara ilişkindir. İlk yazıtta herhangi bir yasaklama, mezar cezası ve lanetleme ifadesi yer almazken, diğesinde “başka birinin gömülmemesi”ne ilişkin bir yasaklama ifadesi verilmiş ve ceza kasası olarak kentin baş tanrısı Zeus Solymeus'a ödenmesi gereken 1500 *denarii* tutarında bir ceza miktarı belirtilmiştir.

Anahtar sözcükler: Termessos, Mezar Yazıtı, Dionysos, Zeus Solymeus, Pisidia

The two epitaphs introduced here were found in the necropolis area numbered E3 of Termessos. In Termessos, ten necropolis areas have been identified, almost all of which include burial structures dating from the Roman Imperial Period. The E3 necropolis lies between Top Tepe, the summit of Güllük Mountain, and the lower rocky hill rising to the west, and on the eastern slopes of

* Assoc. Dr., Akdeniz University, Faculty of Letters, Department of Ancient Languages and Cultures, Antalya. nihaltuner@akdeniz.edu.tr | 0000-0002-1098-028X

** Prof. Dr., Akdeniz University, Faculty of Letters, Department of History, Antalya. marslan@akdeniz.edu.tr | 0000-0003-1132-7423

this hill¹ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Google Earth photo showing the location of Necropolis Area E3

1. Thoas Builds Sarcophagus for His Son, Hermaios

The sarcophagus, was made of local limestone. It was found in a fairly intact condition in the southeast of the E3 necropolis. It has fallen from above and has collapsed on its front face. Its lid most probably fell into the lower valley. The three-line inscription is engraved unframed on the upper edge of the front long side of the sarcophagus. There is no *tabula ansata*. On the inscribed main face of the sarcophagus, there are two round shield depictions, close to the right and left sides, carved on the surface without a frame.

Inv.no: TER2019_41.

Coordinates: 36°58'58" N - 30°27'58" E; Altitude: 960 m; fallibility: app. 10 m.

Dimensions: Length: 212 cm; Depth: 80 cm; Height: 85cm; L.H.: 2.7-3.4 cm.

Date: Before Constitutio Antoniniana (212 A.D.)².

¹ For the Termessos necropolis areas, see Çelgin 1990, 72-89; For the E3 necropolis, see also 77-78.

² The owner of the tomb and his son did not receive Aurelius *nomen gentilicium*.

ἱερεὺς ΠΡΟΙΜΩΝ μεγάλου θεοῦ Δι[ονύσ]- *Thoas, son of Thoas, son of Arteimas, priest of*
 2 ου Θόας δις Ἀρτεϊμου, τὴν θήκην Ἑρ- *the Supreme God Dionysus, one of the ancient*
 μαίω τῷ υἱῷ αὐτοῦ. *gods(?), built this sarcophagus for his own*
son, Hermaios.

L. 1. As can be understood from this line, the person who built the tomb was a priest of Dionysus. Three suggestions can be made for transcription of the letters ΠΡΟΙΜΩΝ after the first word of this, but each of them has different handicaps in itself. The first suggestion is ἱερεὺς πρό(βουλος) <ι>ήμῶν. As shown in the completion here, it can be either a haplography or that the letter iota was used instead of eta³. The name of this official position, considered to be a member of a ten-person board headed by a manager (ἀρχιπρόβουλος) and to be interested in urban affairs, appears mostly as an abbreviation (mostly in the form of προ(όβουλος) in urban inscriptions⁴. In some inscriptions, it is seen that this officer also performed the duty of priesthood. In this case, the abbreviation ΠΡΟΙ is often interpreted as προ(βούλου) ἱ(ερέως)⁵. This abbreviation appears in all of the inscriptions, independently of the honor, dedication, dedication or other subjects that constitute the content of the relevant inscription, at the end and mostly in the part where the name of the eponym officer is given⁶. Since the name ἱερεὺς, which indicates that the owner of the tomb is the priest of the Supreme God Dionysus, is mentioned at the beginning in our inscription, the abbreviation of ΠΡΟΙ cannot be interpreted as πρό(βουλος) ἱ(ερέως) as in the inscriptions given for example by being separated from the letters ΜΩΝ. There is no example for the transcription suggested to be made as ἱερεὺς πρό(βουλος) <ι>ήμῶν. In addition, in any inscription where πρό(βουλος) is used alone, ἡμῶν is not followed by this word.

The second suggestion is made through the transcription πρὸ <ι>ήμῶν by going over the possibility that no abbreviation has been used. However, such a use is unknown to the present. It is known that the preposition πρὸ with the title of priest is mostly used as “ἱερεὺς πρὸ πόλεως”. The formulation “Πρὸ πόλεως” has been interpreted by some researchers as indicating the temple or sanctuary of the god, located “in front of the city, out of the city” due to the locative use of the preposition πρὸ⁷. However, it is thought that its use in addition to the priesthood title should be understood more causally and indicates the special public status of this priesthood⁸.

³ About the use of the letter -ι instead of -η, see Gignac 1976, 235 ff.

⁴ About this official post, see Heberdey 1929, 129; 1934, 763 ff.; TAM III/ 295; Çelgin 1997, 142 ff.

⁵ Cf. TAM III/1.53, 144, 153, 156.

⁶ For the eponymous official posts of M. Aur. Platonianus and M. Aur. Moles and Dioteimos, who also assumed the lifelong priesthood of God Dionysus, see TAM III/1 s. 295.

⁷ For the use of the πρὸ πόλεως formulation, see Le Bas & Waddington 1972, 373. M Holleaux (1986, 235 ff. no. 14) also deduced from the expression ἱερεὺς πρὸ πόλεως Λητοῦς in an epitaph from Oinoanda that the temple of Leto was outside the city, in front of the gates. πρὸ πόλεως, which was found in Metropolis and used for the priesthood of the god Ares, was also evaluated as the god was located outside the city as the protector of the city. Cf. SEG LIX 1352.

⁸ J. & L Robert (1983, 171-176) argue that the formulation of πρὸ πόλεως, used in addition to the title of priest,

From this point of view, if the transcription of *ιερεὺς πρὸ ἡμῶν μεγάλου θεοῦ Δι[ονύσ]ου* is accepted, a translation of “*priest of the supreme god Dionysus (the one) for our benefit*” or “*priest of our protective⁹ supreme god Dionysus*” can be suggested.

The third proposal is based upon the use of *πρόιμων* = *πρώμων*¹⁰. The three-ending adjective *πρώμιος*, which comes from the same origin as the words *πρωί* and *πρώιος* as a word, gives the meaning of “early” in cyclically repeating periods of time¹¹. It is learned in the inscription on the reused limestone slab on the floor of the burial chamber of St. Nicholas church dated to the Hellenistic Period, which was registered in 1965 by Cl. Brixhe and introduced without comment by A.-V. Schweyer in 2002 (2002, 259 no. 72), that a man named as Albasis from Myra was the priest of “*πρώμοι θεοί*”. Before this, it was not determined that this adjective was used together with any god or the word “*θεός*”. Th. Corsten (2008, 102 ff.) tried to interpret the gods mentioned here both in the literal meaning of the word and through his consultations with the relevant scientists¹² in his study interpreting this inscription: “*Gods of First Crops*”, “*Gods of Red Dawn*”, “*Heirloom Gods*”, “*Gods of the Old Generation*” and “*Gods of too Early Deaths*”. Since these gods are associated with the damnation of crime against the tomb in the Albasis epitaph, it is suggested that they can be compared with the “*underground gods*”, which are generally associated with the damnation of those who commit crimes against the tomb in Lycian epitaphs and called (*κατα*)*χθόνιοι θεοί* or *πατρῶιοι θεοί*; in addition, the possibility that the “*ancient Gods*” of the previous generation, who were pushed to the underworld in Near Eastern myths, might be the equivalents of the Lycian pantheon is discussed.

A second document regarding these gods was found in the ancient settlement of Köybaşı, located 8 km north of Kalkan in 2010. The words read at the beginning of the eighth line of this inscription, in which a woman named Paua, the daughter of Hermagenes, presented the statue votive to her husband Hieratikos, were transcribed as *καὶ τῶν πρώιμων θε[ῶν]*¹³. Schuler (2010, 80ff.) prefers to interpret these gods as “*gods of the early morning crops, or, gods of the early ripe crops*”. D. Schürr (2012, 213-224) wrote an article about the “*Early Gods*” of Lycia by considering both these inscriptions in 2011. Here, he argues that the “*Early gods*” are not of Hellenic origin, but rather that they can be accepted as the Lycian equivalents of the “*Old Gods*” in connection with the Hittites, and suggests that the adjective *πρωίμιος* corresponds to the cognate Lycian *prze/i*¹⁴.

If the transcription of *ιερεὺς προίμων μεγάλου θεοῦ Δι[ονύσ]ου* in this epitaph from Termessos is accepted, then, as in the other two inscriptions, the adjective *πρωίμων* given in the

is used more for cults of “*the chief god of the city*” or the “*protector god*” rather than referring to a cult outside the city walls. Ch. Schuler (2010, 71) also refers to the usages in Asia Minor, based on the expression “[*ιερέα πρὸ πόλεως*], which he proposes as a complement in an honorary inscription found at the Köybaşı location of Western Lycia, and agrees with J. & L Robert’s conclusions, emphasizing that this term should have indicated the special public status of the priesthood, rather than meaning the “*cults in front of the city*” and discusses the use of eponyms especially in Lycian examples (Schuler 2010, 74-81). D. Reitzenstein (2014, 553) suggested that this expression in *τὸν ιερέα πρὸ πόλεως δι[ὰ βίου Κρό]νου μεγάλου θεοῦ* definition mentioned in the honorary inscription for a Kronos priest in Tlos was the chief god of the city (Reitzenstein 2014, 555). In Termessos, a priest named Otanes was introduced as *ὁ καὶ πρὸ πόλεως | ιερεὺς Οτάνης* without any name of a god in the inscription on the heroon which he had built (TAM III/ 695).

⁹ Since the chief god of Termessos was Zeus Solymeus, it is more logical that it was used here as a protective god. About this subject, see Çelgin 2001-2002, 122.

¹⁰ For the use of the letter -o instead of -ω, see. Gignac 1976, 275-277.

¹¹ Liddell & Scott 1940, s.v. *πρωίμιος*.

¹² Corsten 2008, 102 fn. 27 (Chr. Kokkinia); 28 (F. Gschnitzer) and 30 (A. Chaniotis).

¹³ Schuler 2010, 71. Cf. Şahin 2010, 140.

¹⁴ Schürr 2012, 218-222.

plural genetivus casus is not followed by the word θεῶν as expected, instead, this adjective is followed by the phrase μεγάλου θεοῦ in singularis genetivus casus. However, it should be noted that the word θεῶν is completed in the inscription from Köybaşı. Therefore, according to the transcription proposal for our epitaph, it can be suggested that the “Supreme God Dionysus” was regarded as among the “Ancient Gods” or “Underground Gods” in Termessos, by accepting a genetivus partitivus phrase. In this case, documenting the “Ancient Gods”, which are interpreted as the local gods of the Lycian region, as discussed above, in a Pisidian city will cause a new perspective to be brought to these interpretations.

Eight inscriptions mentioning the priest of the god Dionysus have been documented in Termessos to date¹⁵. Through these epitaphs, Oples son of Obrimotes, Oples son of Obrolamos and M. Aur. Platonianus Otanes are known to have been priests of Dionysus in Termessos. M. Aur. Platonianus Otanes is also a proboulos. With the epitaph introduced here, a new priest may be added to the list: Thoas, son of Thoas, grandson of Arteimas. It is thought that the temple, identified as N6 in Termessos, may belong to the god Dionysus, among others, since its location is closest to the theater¹⁶. While no description or epithet is used for the god in other inscriptions from the city, he is usually mentioned with the Goddess Rome and the Emperor Cult. He is mentioned alone in only one inscription (*TAM* III/1. 841). The definition of “The Supreme God” for God is also documented in an inscription from Attaleia, apart from Termessos¹⁷.

LL. 2/3: In these lines, it is learned that Thoas, the son of Thoas, the son of Arteimas, had this tomb built for his son Hermaios. In another epitaph documented at Termessos, it is learned that his daughter Manona had a tomb built for her father Thoas (*TAM* III/1. 588: Μανωνα, ἱερέως Θό|αντος δις Αρτειμου | θυγάτηρ, γυνή δὲ Νέω|νος Αρτειμου Νέωνο|[ς], τὴν θήκην Θόαντι, | τῷ πατρὶ αὐτῆς. Manona's father Thoas must be the same person as the Thoas in the epitaph discussed here. In both epitaphs, the ἡ θήκη definition is identified as the type of tomb. It is thought that the nomenclature ἡ θήκη in the epitaphs indicates the body of this sarcophagus, if it is on a sarcophagus; if in a rock tomb, it indicates a burial chamber¹⁸. In both epitaphs, there is no prohibition, penalty charge or damnation phrase.

2. Epitaph of Claudia Anna and Her Family

The sarcophagus is made of local limestone. It was found in the middle part of the E3 necropolis, close to the valley, overturned on its long inscribed face. The sarcophagus is in a very good condition. Only a large piece has been broken off from the lower right corner of the back side. Its lid is overturned on one of its sides, about one and a half meters east of it. On the front of the body of this sarcophagus there is a *tabula ansata* on the surface without a frame, and a round shield relief on both sides of it. The first line of the epitaph with 9 lines is engraved on the side of the sarcophagus on the *tabula*, and the second line is engraved on the upper frame of the *tabula*; 3-8. rows are in the *tabula*, and the 9th row is beneath the *tabula*.

Inv. No : TER2019_46.

Coordinate: 36°59'01" N - 30°27'60" E; Altitude: 990 m; Fallibility: approx. 10m

Dimensions: Length: 220 cm; Width: 108 cm; Height: 110 cm; L.H.:1.5-7.5 cm.

Date: After 212 A.D.

¹⁵ *TAM* III/1. 105-16, 108-110, 153, 156 and 841.

¹⁶ For this issue, see Çelgin 1997, 176.

¹⁷ *IGR* III 780.

¹⁸ See Kubinska 1968, 39-40; Schweyer 2002, 21. About the typology of the sarcophagus in Termessos, see Çelgin 1994, 163-168.

- Κλ(αυδία) Άννα τήν σωματοθήκην ἑαυτῆ καὶ Συριάρχῃ
 2 καὶ υἱῷ Κλ(αυδίῳ) Ἑρμιανῷ καὶ τῆ ἀδελφῆ Αὐρ(ηλία) Οα
 καὶ τῷ προενειμέ-
 4 νῳ αὐτῆς ἀν-
 δρί· ἄλλῳ δὲ οὐ-
 6 δενὶ ἔξεσται
 ἐπιθάψαι τινὰ
 8 ἐπεὶ δώσει προσ-
 τείμου Διὶ Σολυμεῖ Ἧ,αφ'

Claudia Anna built this tomb for herself and Syriarkhes, as well as for her son Claudius Hermianos and her sister Aurelia Oa and her previously deceased husband; no one else is allowed to bury someone, otherwise 1500 denarii will be paid to Zeus Solymeus as punishment.

Claudia/Claudius nomen gentilicium received by the tomb owner Anna and her son Hermianos indicates a citizenship right associated with the Emperor Claudius. The fact that his sister Oa was recorded as Aurelia gens is related to the *Constitutio Antoniniana*. Oa is an epicoric name and is documented in many inscriptions at Termessos¹⁹. The identity of Syriarkhes, a name of ethnarkh (= national leader) origin like Lykiarkhes, Asiarkhes and frequently documented in

¹⁹ Zgusta 1964, 386 § 1129-2.

Termessos, is not clearly stated, but her husband's name is not mentioned in the epitaph where it is recorded that Anna had the tomb built for her previously deceased husband as well. In most of Termessos epitaphs, the person whose name is mentioned in the second row is recorded as the wife/husband of the tomb owner, regardless of whether it is a man or a woman. Therefore, it can be thought conceivable that Syriarkhes would have been Anna's husband, but it is noteworthy that he did not take any gens name.

Zeus Solymeus, the chief god of the city, was determined as the authorized recipient of fines for crimes against the tomb²⁰.

²⁰ For the inscriptions in which Zeus Solymeus was identified as the recipient for fines in the epitaphs in the city and the amount, see İplikçioğlu *et al.* 2007, 317-320; cf. Akçay & Gurel 2018, 10 ff. fn. 27.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Akçay A. & Gürel B. 2018, "Görülenin Ötesine Gitmek: Sayısal Görüntüleme Metodları Işığında Termessos'tan Sütunlu Bir Lahit Üzerine Yeni Değerlendirmeler". Eds. M. Arslan & F. Baz, *Arkeoloji, Tarih ve Epigrafi'nin Arasında: Prof. Dr. Vedat Çelgin'in 68. Doğum Günü Onuruna Makaleler*. İstanbul, 1-18.
- Corsten T. 2008, "Die Grabinschrift des Priesters Albasis in Myra". *Adalya* 11, 99-107.
- Çelgin A. V. 1990, *Termessos Kenti Nekropol'leri*. Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi, İstanbul Üniversitesi. İstanbul.
- Çelgin A. V. 1994, "Termessos ve Çevresinde Nekropol ve Epigrafi Araştırmaları: 1975-1991 Yılları Arasında Yapılan Çalışmaların Toplu Sonuçlarına Kısa Bir Bakış". *Anadolu Araştırmaları* 13, 153-177.
- Çelgin A. V. 1997, *Termessos Tarihi*. İstanbul.
- Çelgin A. V. 2001-2002, "Termessos Tanrıları ve Kent Alanından Artemis'in Yeni Epithet ve Kültlerini Belgeleyen Üç Yazıt (Bir Ön Değerlendirme)". *Adalya* 5, 121-136.
- Gignac F. T. 1976, *A Grammar of the Greek Papyri of the Roman and Byzantine Periods I-II*. Milano.
- Heberdey R. 1929, *Termessische Studien*. Wien – Leipzig.
- Heberdey R. 1934, "Termessos No. 2". *Pauly-Wissowa's Realecyclopädie* II/9. Stuttgart, 732-775.
- Holleaux M. 1986, "Inscriptions D'Oenoanda". *BCH* 10, 216-235.
- İplikçioğlu B., A. V. Çelgin & G. Çelgin 2007, *Epigraphische Forschungen in Termessos und seinem Territorium IV*. Wien.
- Kubinska J. 1968, *Les monuments funéraires dans les inscriptions grecques de l'Asie Mineure*. Warsaw.
- le Bas P. & Waddington W. H. 1972, *Inscriptions grecques et latines recueillies en Grèce et en Asie Mineure II: Textes en Minuscules et Explications*. Hildesheim – New York.
- Liddell H. G. & Scott R. 1940, *A Greek and English Lexicon*. Oxford.
- Reitzenstein D. 2014, "Neue Inschriften aus Tlos: Kronoskult, Agonistik und Euergetismus". *Chiron* 44, 551-612.
- Robert J. & Robert L. 1983, *Fouilles d'Amyzon en Carie I: Exploration, Histoire, Monnaies et Inscriptions*. Paris.
- Schuler Ch. 2010, "Priester πρὸ πόλεως, in Lykien: Eine neue Inschrift aus dem Territorium von Patara". *ZPE* 173, 69-86.
- Schürr D. 2012, "'Frühe Götter' in Lykien". *Archiv für Religionsgeschichte* 13, 213-224.
- Schweyer A.-V. 2002, *Les Lyciens et la mort. Une Etude d'Histoire Sociale*. Paris.
- SEG Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum*.
- Şahin S. 2010, "Parerga zum Stadiasmus Patarensis (3). Die Inschrift von Köybaşı in Zentrallykien". *Gephyra* 7, 137-152.
- TAM Tituli Asia Minoris*. Vindobonae 1901 – 1989.
- Zgusta L. 1964, *Kleinasiatische Personennamen*. Prague.